

MULTIFUNCTIONAL MICROVASCULAR COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Complex multidimensional vascular polymers are fabricated by using sacrificial material templates. The sacrificial material consists of the commodity biopolymer poly(lactic) acid (PLA) treated with a tin catalyst to accelerate thermal depolymerization. We show that these materials can be formed into sacrificial templates across multiple dimensions and spanning several orders of magnitude in size scale. Templates are then embedded in a thermosetting polymer and removed using a thermal treatment process leaving behind an inverse replica of the template material. The effectiveness of VaSC is verified both *ex situ* and *in situ*, and the resulting structures are validated via flow rate testing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Modern composites are highly engineered materials systems that continue a steady evolution towards increased complexity. An expanding set of performance goals and objectives drives their design beyond the historical focus on strength, stiffness, and fracture toughness. Instead, composites have evolved into multifunctional, integrated materials systems. This approach finds precedence in biology where multifunctional materials systems are commonplace. One hallmark of multifunctional systems in biology is their reliance on a vascular network for transport of nutrients, chemical compounds, energy, etc. in a circulating fluid stream. At the University of Illinois we have developed techniques to seamlessly integrated vascular networks in fiber-reinforced composites in order to create multifunctional materials systems containing both solid and fluidic elements.

2 VAPORIZATION OF SACRIFICIAL COMPONENTS (VASC)

In the past, several approaches have been used for fabricating three-dimensional (3D) microvascular networks including lithographic techniques, laser micromachining, and various two-dimensional methods extended to 3D. More recently we have shown that vaporization of sacrificial components (VaSC) can be used to create structural composites containing complex, 3D microvascular networks [1,2]. Generally, we utilize sacrificial fibers that are co-woven with the reinforcing fibers then removed via thermal treatment at elevated temperature. The fibers depolymerize to a gaseous monomer leaving behind networks of interconnected empty channels that can be filled with a functional fluid.

Sacrificial materials are made by combining PLA pellets (NatureWorks LLC) and a tin octoate (SnOc) catalyst (Sigma-Aldrich) at a concentration between 1-5 wt%. We show that various geometric precursors from spheres (0D) to fibers (1D) to sheets (2D) and finally, printed (3D) structures can be fabricated.

Fig. 1. Vascular composites prepared by VaSC processing. (a) Open cell porous epoxy prepared by a sintered sacrificial polymer template of catalyst doped PLA microspheres. (b) 3D branched multiscale vascular network embedded in epoxy prepared by 3D printing of catalyst doped PLA.

3 CHARACTERIZATION AND ASSESSMENT

We performed a variety of characterization and assessment experiments to demonstrate dimensional fidelity and efficiency of the VaSC process. Optical and electron microscopy was used to measure porosity and feature sizes. Flow rate experiments were carried out to measure permeability and validate our structures with respect to accepted fluid flow models. We use microCT data coupled with computational fluid dynamics modeling to predict flow profiles and provide benchmarks for experimental results.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Microvascular composites can perform a variety of multifunctional tasks. In fact, the same vascular composite demonstrates pluripotent functionality that is differentiated by the types of fluid circulated in the vascular network. For example, circulation of coolants can raise the operational temperature of polymer matrix composites [3]. Circulating healing agents in the same type of composite can then lead to repeated recovery of mechanical performance after damage [4]. We will summarize the state of art in multifunctional performance of microvascular composites and the future use of multifunctional fluids (e.g. coolants that provide chemical healing) will be discussed.

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